

Classification of Breast Micro-Calcifications as Benign or Malignant using Subtraction of Temporally Sequential Digital Mammograms and Machine Learning

Kosmia Loizidou¹, Galateia Skouromouni², Gabriella Savvidou³, Anastasia Constantinidou⁴, Christos Nikolaou⁴, and Costas Pitris¹

¹ KIOS Research and Innovation Center of Excellence, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus cloizi01@ucy.ac.cy

² Radiology Department, German Oncology Center, Limassol, Cyprus

³ Medical School University of Cyprus and the Bank of Cyprus Oncology Centre, Nicosia, Cyprus

⁴ Radiology Department, Limassol General Hospital, Limassol, Cyprus

Abstract. Cancer ranks as the second leading cause of mortality worldwide with breast cancer accounting for approximately 20% of all new cancer cases reported globally. Mammography is the most effective screening tool for the early diagnosis of breast cancer. However, the current practice of evaluating mammograms by two radiologists, and a third in case of disagreement, highlights the challenges faced even by experts in identifying potential abnormalities. To address these challenges, Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems are being developed to assist radiologists in breast cancer diagnosis. This study proposes a classification approach for biopsy-confirmed benign and malignant Micro-Calcifications (MCs), using subtraction of temporally sequential digital mammograms combined with feature-based machine learning. The algorithm's performance was evaluated on a dataset retrospectively collected for this work, including 128 images from 32 patients, with precisely annotated MC locations and biopsy confirmations. Several features were extracted and a combination of feature selection algorithms was employed to identify the most critical subset of features. Ten classifiers were evaluated using leave-one-patient-out and k-fold cross-validation ($k = 4$ and 8). An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) achieved the highest performance, with 90.63% sensitivity, and 85.39% accuracy. These findings demonstrate the potential of the proposed algorithm to be translated into clinical practice as a second-reading tool for the classification of breast MCs as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant.

Keywords: breast cancer · Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) · digital mammography · temporal subtraction · machine learning.

1 Introduction

Cancer, is the second leading cause of global mortality. According to the American Cancer Society (ACS), in the United States alone approximately 3,200,000 new cancer cases and 904,000 deaths are expected by 2040 [4]. Among these cases, breast cancer accounts for approximately 20% and $\sim 30\%$ of all female cancers [2]. Mammography, the key screening tool for breast cancer diagnosis, dropped the mortality of the disease by about 42%, and significantly improved patient prognosis [11]. Current protocols require evaluation by two radiologists, and the involvement of a third expert, in case of a disagreement. However, when it comes to dense breast tissue, mammograms exhibit increased intensity and variations that closely resemble certain abnormalities. Due to this similarity, the sensitivity of mammography is reduced by approximately 30%, resulting in an elevated risk of breast cancer [12].

Micro-Calcifications (MCs) inside a mammogram are considered suspicious signs that warrant further assessment. They appear as bright spots due to the higher X-ray attenuation coefficient of calcium, compared to surrounding normal breast tissue [15]. Radiological classification of breast MCs as benign or suspicious relies on crucial parameters such as shape, texture, and distribution. Although the majority of MCs are benign and do not need intervention, Micro-Calcification Clusters (MCCs) are considered precursors to cancer [13]. In the case of a suspicious finding, a biopsy will confirm whether it is malignant. Accurate classification of benign and malignant MCs remains a challenge due to their small size, wide morphological variations, and the high intensity of the background. Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems aim to assist radiologists in the detection and classification of breast MCs by exploiting advanced algorithms and machine learning techniques [11].

The classification of biopsy-confirmed benign vs. malignant MCs has gained significant attention in the literature, leading to the development of various algorithms [11]. However, the vast majority of these studies utilize only the most recent mammographic view of a patient, neglecting the importance to compare prior images of the same patient. These comparisons are routinely conducted by clinicians to identify newly developed abnormalities, or regions displaying rapid changes between the screenings and are often considered suspicious [16]. Temporal analysis is proposed in the literature for the comparison of sequential mammograms, and it has been applied for the detection and classification of breast MCs [11]. However, studies based on temporal analysis offer no advantage over utilizing only the most recent mammographic view, when the abnormality is entirely new, with no traces in prior examinations.

In this work, an algorithm that combines subtraction of temporally sequential mammograms with feature-based machine learning for the classification of breast MCs as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant is proposed. Temporal subtraction, previously introduced by this research group, has shown significant advantages in the detection and radiological classification of breast MCs [9], and masses [10]. A new dataset was collected specifically for this study. Pre-processing was first applied, and then, image registration along with temporal

Fig. 1. Dataset example. **(A)** Recent Mammogram. **(B)** A closer view of the area outlined by the red square in **(A)**, showing MCs and a Micro-Calcification Cluster (MCC). **(C)** The region in **B** with precise annotation of MC and MCC locations, as annotated by two expert radiologists. The green arrows in **C** indicate benign MCs, while the red arrow indicates the suspicious MCC.

subtraction took place. Following, the detection and segmentation were performed and subsequently, various features were extracted and ranked using five feature selection algorithms. The suspicious MCs were classified as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant using the most successful methodology.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Data Collection and Description

A dataset containing 32 pairs of full-field digital mammograms (from women 38 to 83 years) with both benign and suspicious MCs in their most recent mammographic images, was retrospectively collected from local hospitals. Inclusion in the study necessitated the availability of a normal, or benign prior mammographic view, with an average interval of 2 years.

For every participant, two mammographic views, the Cranio-Caudal (CC, view from above) and Medio-Lateral Oblique (MLO, angled view) were collected. Two sequential screening rounds were included for every participant, resulting in a database with a total of 128 images ($2 \times 2 \times 32$). An expert radiologist selected the eligible patients, and along with a second radiologist, assessed the mammograms to mark the MCs as radiological benign or suspicious. Suspicious cases were subsequently confirmed as malignant through biopsies, followed by histopathological analysis. Among the 32 women who underwent biopsies, 21 had biopsy-confirmed benign MCs, 5 had biopsy-confirmed malignant MCs, and 6 were diagnosed with Ductal Carcinoma In Situ (DCIS), which is recognized as the earliest form of breast cancer. For the purposes of this study, the biopsy-confirmed malignant cases and the cases diagnosed with DCIS were considered as 1-class associated with malignancies. This is the first dataset that includes temporally sequential digital mammograms, along with precise annotations of each individual MC (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Effect of pre-processing. (A) Original recent image. (B) A closer view of the area outlined by the red square in A showing an area with MCs. (C) A closer view of the area outlined by the green square in A, showing an area without MCs. (D) Image after border removal. (E) Final processed image after gamma correction. (F) A closer view of the area outlined by the red square in E, showing the same area as B, after pre-processing. (G) A closer view of the area outlined by the green square in E, showing the same area as C, after pre-processing.

2.2 MCs Detection and Segmentation

Normalization, border removal, and gamma correction were applied consecutively to both recent and prior mammographic views, to eliminate unnecessary information. Border removal was employed to effectively eliminate high-intensity regions connected to the border, including the pectoral muscle in the MLO views [6]. Subsequently, gamma correction was implemented to enhance the contrast of the images by suppressing low-intensity regions, producing a new filtered image with high-intensity areas and thus, possible breast abnormalities [8]. Figure 2 presents an example of the pre-processing steps applied.

Recent and prior mammographic views were then registered to account for variations in breast compression, changes in breast shape, and potential human error during screening. Various image registration techniques were developed specifically for mammograms [11]. Demons registration [14] was selected in this case, as it effectively tracked the MCs changes over time, without introducing any errors. After the registration, temporal subtraction was performed by subtracting the prior-registered mammogram, from the recent one. An example of temporal subtraction is presented in Figure 3. To evaluate the effectiveness of the subtraction, a comparison was conducted between the Contrast Ratio (CR) of the subtracted image and the CR of the most recent mammogram, without any pre-processing.

The subtracted image underwent further processing using a range filter, to further enhance the abnormalities and remove any unnecessary areas [1]. Segmentation of Regions of Interest (ROIs) followed, using a three-step procedure: thresholding, application of morphological operations, and elimination of the periphery pixels. Initially, the images were converted into binary through thresholding, enabling the elimination of low-intensity regions. The threshold value was chosen to optimize the global classification rate. Subsequently, the binary

Fig. 3. Example of temporal subtraction. (A) Most recent mammogram. (B) Prior mammogram. (C) Subtracted image created after subtracting the registered version of B from A. (D-F) A closer view of the areas outlined by the red squares in A-C. The rectangles enclose suspicious MCs, which were not subtracted.

image underwent morphological processing, using erosion and closing. Erosion was employed with a radius of 1 pixel, which is smaller than the typical radius of an MC, while closing was applied with a radius of 10 pixels, to identify the constituents of MCCs. In the final step, high-intensity regions that could potentially lead to areas falsely identified as MCs were eliminated. These regions correspond to the skin of the breast, which can not contain MCs but may not be entirely removed during the registration and subtraction process due to misalignment. For the training of the algorithms, the ground truth provided by the radiologists was used.

2.3 Feature Extraction and Selection

In total 96 features were extracted from each suspicious MC, taking into consideration the characteristics that are routinely assessed by clinicians to determine the suspicion level of an MC. These features were divided into four categories: shape, intensity, First-Order Statistics (FOS), and Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix (GLCM) features. They included: area, circularity, compactness, convex area, eccentricity, equivalent diameter, Euler number, extent, filled area, major and minor axis length, orientation, perimeter, solidity, shape ratio, average, minimum, and maximum intensity, entropy, kurtosis, skewness, smoothness, standard deviation, variance, contract, correlation, energy, and homogeneity. Each GLCM feature was extracted at four different angles (0° , 45° , 90° , and 135°) and the mean and standard deviation (STD) were calculated, resulting in 24 values for each offset D . To determine the most suitable offset, three values were tested ($D_1 = 5$, $D_2 = 15$, and $D_3 = 25$). Consequently, a total of 72 GLCM features were extracted.

Table 1. Feature ranking using different feature selection techniques. Selected features are highlighted in bold.

t-test	MRMR	Feature Importance Random Forest	Feature Importance Extra Trees	SelectKBest
Area	Area	Area	Area	Area
Major axis length	Major axis length	Major axis length	Major axis length	Major axis length
Minor axis length	Minor axis length	Minor axis length	Minor axis length	Minor axis length
Eccentricity	Eccentricity	Eccentricity	Eccentricity	Eccentricity
Convex area	Convex area	Convex area	Orientation	Convex area
Filled area	Euler number	Filled area	Convex area	Filled area
Euler number	Equivalent diameter	Equivalent diameter	Filled area	Euler number
Equivalent diameter	Solidity	Solidity	Equivalent diameter	Equivalent diameter
Solidity	Extent	Extent	Solidity	Solidity
Extent	Minimum intensity	Maximum intensity	Extent	Extent
Perimeter	Contrast STD D3	Skewness	Perimeter	Perimeter
Circularity	Circularity	Kurtosis	Average intensity	Skewness
Compactness	Compactness	STD	Maximum intensity	Contrast 90° D1
Shape ratio	Shape ratio	Correlation 0° D1	Skewness	Contrast 135° D1
		Correlation 45° D1	Kurtosis	Contrast mean D1
		Correlation 45° D2	Correlation 45° D2	Contrast 0° D2
		Correlation 90° D3	Correlation 90° D3	Contrast 90° D2
		Circularity	Circularity	Contrast 135° D2
		Compactness	Compactness	Contrast mean D2
		Shape ratio	Shape ratio	Contrast 45° D3

Feature selection was necessary to eliminate unnecessary features and improve the classification performance. A comparison was conducted between five methods: t-test, Maximum Relevance-Minimum Redundancy (MRMR), feature importance, using both random forest and extra trees, and, SelectKBest. As seen in Table 1, each feature selection algorithm produced different feature rankings, since they rely on unique principles. Thus, to identify the most significant features, the results from all methods were combined by applying a majority rule (i.e. keep the high-ranked features from all the methods), and a new feature vector was created (features in bold in Table 1). With this approach, the classification accuracy was increased, compared to using a single feature selection technique.

As is often the case in real-life scenarios, this dataset was imbalanced, with unequal numbers of benign and malignant MCs (229 benign vs. 32 malignant). To address this issue, Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was employed, and new instances of the minority class were generated in the training set [3]. Feature pre-processing was also applied using least squares (l2) normalization, to scale all the samples and adjust the range of their values.

2.4 Training and Comparison of Classifier Designs

Nine classifiers were evaluated for the classification task, including Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Naive Bayes (NB), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), AdaBoost (ADA), Bagging (BAG), Gradient Boosting (GB), and Voting, using Python (v. 3.7.7), and Scikit-learn (v. 0.23.1). Different Artificial Neural Network (ANN) configurations were also evaluated using Keras (v. 2.3.1). Eleven patients were associated with biopsy-confirmed malignancies, thus, their correct identification was cru-

Table 2. Comparison of the classification results in suspicious MCs as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant using LOPO CV

Classifier	Sensitivity [%]	Specificity [%]	Accuracy [%]	AUC
LDA	75.00	66.38	67.42	0.71
k-NN	78.13	69.36	70.41	0.74
SVM	93.75	64.26	67.79	0.79
NB	81.25	60.43	62.92	0.71
MLP	90.63	68.09	70.79	0.79
ADA	50.00	76.60	73.41	0.63
BAG	43.75	82.98	78.28	0.63
GB	46.88	80.85	76.78	0.64
Voting	87.50	61.70	64.79	0.76
ANN	90.63	84.68	85.39	0.88

cial since they need immediate attention. Conversely, 21 women underwent an unnecessary biopsy, as it turned out later, and their suspicious abnormalities were eventually benign. However, it is more important to accurately identify patients associated with malignancies, thus the classification was shifted towards the malignant cases.

Regarding the validation approach, Leave-One-Patient-Out (LOPO) Cross-Validation (CV) was used during training, along with k-fold CV ($k = 4$ and 8). This approach was critical, in order to ensure that the algorithm was working only with unknown patients, thus, to avoid bias from adding images of the same patient in both the test and training sets. Similarly, in k-fold CV the folds were created per patient, rather than randomly dividing the MCs. The suspicious MCs were classified as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant. The performance was evaluated by computing sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and the Area Under the receiver operating characteristic Curve (AUC).

3 Experimental Results

An average reduction of 65% in image intensity was achieved using image registration and subtraction, a result of removing structures that have remained unchanged between screenings. The average CR of the subtracted images was ~ 50 times higher compared to the recent mammographic view. The processing time for these operations was an average of ~ 15 min per image pair (Intel® Core™ i7 2 GHz; Intel Corp., Santa Clara, CA, USA).

Feature selection identified the most important features for the classification task (features in bold in Table 1) and those features were added into the classifiers that were optimized using LOPO CV. The highest classification performance was achieved using an ANN in a LOPO CV scheme, with 90.63% sensitivity, 84.68% specificity, 85.39% accuracy, and 0.88 AUC (Table 2). For the LDA, the linear discriminant criterion was used, without prior probabilities. As for the k-NN, the number of k nearest neighbors was set to 11, and

Fig. 4. Classification results of the MCs as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant using various classifiers and CV methods.

the nearest tie-breaking algorithm was selected. SVM was implemented using a polynomial kernel. NB was implemented using the normal distribution. For the Ensemble Voting, polynomial SVM, NB, and MLP were combined in a hard voting scheme. The selected ANN architecture consisted of 1 hidden layer (96) with 5,714 trainable parameters. ReLU activation function was employed in the input and hidden layers, and softmax activation function in the output layer. Adam optimizer was selected, and batch normalization, dropout regularization, and Gaussian noise regularization were incorporated to enhance the network’s robustness. The batch size was set to 128, the learning rate was 0.0001, and the network was trained for 100 epochs. In addition, k-fold CV ($k = 4$ and 8) was employed to validate the robustness of the method (Fig. 4).

4 Discussion

An ANN reached 90.63% accuracy using LOPO CV, with an average of 0.6 false positives per image for the classification of the MCs as biopsy-confirmed benign or malignant. Although some misclassifications occurred, the clinical impact would have been minimal if the algorithm was actually implemented. Out of 32 malignant MCs, 3 were misclassified as benign, in 2 patients. However, these 2 patients had other malignancies, thus their care would not have been compromised. To evaluate the robustness of the method, k-fold CV was implemented, in addition to LOPO CV. In this case, the performance experienced a slight drop since fewer patients were included in each training round, compared to the 32 patients in the LOPO CV scheme. This drop exemplifies the need for additional training data, while also demonstrating the algorithm’s potential to accurately classify new data.

Given that this is the first application of temporal subtraction for this task, direct comparison with other state-of-the-art techniques is challenging. However, the findings of this work are more accurate than those reported in the literature

Table 3. Comparison of algorithms for the classification of MCs as benign or malignant using sequential mammograms and feature-based machine learning

Reference	Dataset	Classifier	Validation method	Results ACC [%]	Results AUC
Hadjiiski et al. (2002) [7]	65 pairs	LDA	leave-one-out (per patient)	-	0.87 temporal 0.81 single
Filev et al. (2008) [5]	261 pairs	LDA	leave-one-out (per patient)	-	0.81 temporal 0.72 single
Proposed	32 pairs	ANN	LOPO CV (per patient)	85.39	0.88 temporal

for the classification of benign vs. malignant MCs using sequential mammograms (Table 3), in terms of the AUC. Unlike temporal analysis utilized in the literature, the subtraction of temporally sequential mammograms proposed in this work can effectively track and classify newly developed abnormalities, or regions that changed significantly between the screenings.

Despite the promising results, a larger patient population is required to prove the advantages of combining temporal subtraction with feature-based machine learning. Ideally, the algorithm should also be verified on an independent external dataset. Unfortunately, publicly available databases cannot be utilized for the purposes of this project, since they neither contain sequential mammograms nor include images annotated at the level of individual MCs as in this study.

5 Conclusion

In this study, an algorithm for the classification of biopsy-confirmed benign and malignant breast MCs using a combination of subtraction of temporally sequential digital mammograms, and feature-based machine learning was introduced. Ninety-six features were extracted and ranked using a majority rule, with five different feature selection techniques. The most significant features were subsequently fed to the classifiers. The highest classification performance was achieved using an ANN with 85.39% accuracy and 0.88 AUC. Encouraged by the promising findings, the proposed methodology will be further tested on larger datasets. Deep learning algorithms will also be evaluated if large volumes of annotated data that are needed for proper training of such complex algorithms are collected. Furthermore, the algorithm can be applied to other kind of breast abnormalities in mammograms. The algorithm also has the potential to be translated into clinical practice as a breast cancer classification tool, to assist radiologists in the double reading of mammograms, especially in the Population Screening Program of Cyprus and in less-developed countries.

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